

Challenges Primary School Teachers Face In The Resumption Of Sports Events And Activities Amidst Covid-19 Pandemic

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Abstract

There are no magic elixirs to simply reopen sports in schools. Sports and extracurricular activities happening during regular lunch breaks of a normal school day represent a crucial component of teachers' social and emotional needs. This poses many unanswered questions about the ability of primary school teachers to manage various sporting activities and other major events requiring close contact while adhering to social distancing guidelines and other related health protocols for minimising the rate of infections among teachers. This study investigated the experiences of primary school teachers who teach Physical Education as part of Life Skills curriculum during the COVID-19 pandemic in four primary schools in KwaZulu-Natal. This research is a qualitative interpretive case study of four selected schools in the King Cetshwayo District. Data were obtained from PE teachers through semi-structured research interviews and field observation. They were processed and analysed through data coding, unitising, categorising and the emergence of themes, which became the findings of the study. The findings show that although sporting activities and events violate social distancing guidelines, and heighten the spread of COVID-19 infections to PE teachers as such, PE teachers are facing complex challenges ranging from fear of contracting the virus to taking long protracted leave before the resumption of PE during lockdown. Some are optimistic that a new pedagogy will be found for implementing safe PE and sports culture in rural primary schools to mitigate the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic to PE teachers.

Introduction

Many schools are bound by the intended curriculum to promote active physical activity (PA) through physical education (PE) teaching. However, COVID-19 has disrupted any activity that seeks to promote healthy bodies and minds in schools (Huang, Li-Wei, Chang Hsieh & Lu 2019). The threats from childhood obesity and sedentary behaviour demand urgent intervention, as schools are contemplating to restart PE and PA (Goldstein 2020). The benefit associated with physical activities have been well documented until quite recently when the COVID-19 outbreak forced almost all countries to shutdown schools while trying to rewrite the playbook governing contact sports and PE. There is little doubt that PE teachers love sports and sports practice, not least for athletes, but they have had to change, pause or even cease their activities as a result of the pandemic (Evens et al. 2020). The most striking evidence is the immediate sport disruptions for those that teach sport education in schools, owing to the uncertainty surrounding fundamental overhaul of the way people engage with and instruct sports participants (Huang et al. 2019). Global shutdown or postponement of competitive sport at schools is comprehended in the notion that such "mass gatherings" significantly exacerbate the risks of the spread of the virus (Goldstein 2020).

It is common knowledge that school sports events and other physical activities generate huge revenue and feature scouts looking for talented sports teachers in urban schools, with very few exceptions in rural schools (Jeleff et al. 2019). Sports in rural schools attract less interest from big sponsors than their urban counterparts (Bailey & Hess 2020). Such investment is known to produce world athletes and talents when nurtured as early as primary school level, and is likely to attract professional teams and organisations (Hayden 2015). The reality is that COVID-19 leads to the total suspension of school sports, necessitating the developing practical health guidelines that put the lives of teachers and learners first by suspending sports activities and PE in schools. In essence, the suspension of school sports has inadvertently exposed huge complexities for current funding and endorsements enjoyed by teachers who teach these young sports stars (Goldstein 2020). This scenario, according to Goldstein, poses a serious threat for private and public schools benefiting financially and otherwise

from participating in planned sports events and activities. Bailey and Hess (2020) argue that private and Model C schools will be able to survive the COVID-19 storm, but the school sports infrastructure in lower-income communities, already so hamstrung and underdeveloped, simply will not be geared up to attract more participation when sports activities resume, thus widening the socio-economic gap with organised school sport reserved for the elite. Investment in sports events and activities for rural primary schools remains weaker during COVID-19, and a pipedream for some (Zimu, van Heerden & Grace 2020). The fact that rural schools are more vulnerable to COVID-19 owing to poor healthcare provision is a concern to stakeholders despite few confirmed COVID-19 cases registered to date, which generates less urgency compared to the response in urban schools. Sport and extracurricular activities represent a crucial component of all Foundation Phase (FP) teaching, and there are question marks about when these activities will finally resume, considering the surge in new infections in both primary and high schools (Bailey & Hess 2020). The Department of Health and the Department of Basic Education (DBE) formulated guidelines that prohibit gatherings of teachers in crowds in staffrooms and offices because this pandemic remains a potential health hazard (Super, Wentink, Verkooijen & Koelen 2017). School sports are a perfect means to nurture teachers and learners to be physically active, but this inadvertently increases vulnerability to the danger of infection in contact sports and similar activities. However, the study conducted by Tercedor et al. (2017) stresses the need for adequate PA at the FP level for the prevention of obesity and chronic disease later in life. Sports participation plays an important role in the development of life skills needed later in life for societal domains (Hayden 2015). School recess during the normal day provides the best opportunities to practise and perfect motor skills, which might contribute to up to 40% of children's recommended daily PA (Tercedor et al. 2017). Research suggests that young people can develop a coping mechanism through participation in sport (Super et al. 2017), which they can use later in their careers to deal with life challenges such as obesity and chronic disease. In school, young people develop these traits by participating in group contact sports to undergo developmental experiences, including those related to various stressors in the sports setting (DeNizio & Hewitt 2019). Valuable lessons have been learned in this area. Surprisingly, these studies offer very little information about how schools and caregivers might enforce social distancing as one of the pillars that might prevent teachers from contracting COVID-19 by participating in a sport during daily planned events and activities as part of normal teaching and learning. The question worth asking is: what are the experiences of FP teachers who teach PE as part of Life Skills curriculum during COVID-19 pandemic?

Additionally, the available information suggests that social distancing measures save lives when applied meticulously, but they also impose an irreparable cost on society (Thunstrom et al. 2020). As schools continue to strike a balance between saving the academic year and minimising the chances of contracting COVID-19, vulnerability to risks in taking part in school sport remains a serious challenge for teachers (DBE 2014). Hall, Jones and Klenow (2020) acknowledge that many teachers are learning to become accustomed to the new normal. "Social distancing" and "shelter in place" are now part of everyday vernacular and lifesaving measures. Therefore, many opportunities for teachers to be physically active have been suspended, especially during the school-based PE in primary schools. Put differently, there is an increased risk that arises from social isolation for teachers which impacts seriously on their mental health and physical wellbeing (Hall, Jones & Klenow 2020). As a consequence, school playgrounds have become high risk spaces for the implementation of school-based interventions to promote PA during normal breaks of the day in primary schools (Tercedor et al. 2017). The surge in new COVID-19 cases has forced the DBE to retreat from implementing a blanket phasing-in approach for fear of exposing teachers to this public health hazard called COVID-19 (DBE 2020).

The layout of the literature reviewed is as follows: the first area that has piqued curiosity relates to the fundamental purpose of school sport and the threat it poses to teachers (physical activity and exercise); and to how teachers manage to change their behavior during the COVID-19 pandemic. Serious questions about formats needed as a fresh start to bring certainty and former glory could be key foci. Second, the literature identified possible vulnerabilities considered to have an impact on sports events and activities. Third, the role of the school is considered important during the implementation of sports events and general activities in teaching PE-related activities (Hoadley & Jansen 2013). Fourth, the literature highlights the innovative measures possible to maintain social distancing during sporting events and activities to minimise teachers' vulnerability to contracting COVID-19 during PE activities.

Teachers are vulnerable to contracting COVID-19 in primary schools

Competitive sports that involve extensive contact commonly help to increase the interest in events and are growing in popularity around the world (DeNizio & Hewitt 2019). Because of their strenuous nature, contact sports expose participants to cuts and bruises resulting from violent confrontation, which increases vulnerability to sickness (Young, Fried, Seidler & Eickhoff-Shemek 2014). Some of the vulnerable groups include teachers with existing medical conditions, who may be at high risk of contracting the virus. These cautions lead to the second area of inquiry, that sports events and activities that are organised and supported in primary schools

encourage mass gatherings. However, the UN notes that many poor communities in developing countries continue to marginalise sports and PE in their education systems, despite these being indispensable for physical development, and promotion of a healthy lifestyle (Osborne, Belmont, Peixoto, Azevedo & Carvalho 2016). All teachers need to be extremely cautious when implementing PE curriculum given the vulnerabilities associated with contact sports, as the COVID-19 virus is highly contagious and possibly lethal (Jukic et al 2020).

Some established norms associated with sports gestures, such as sharing drink bottles, hugging, and shaking hands are the antithesis, in an arena packed with spectators, of social distancing (Neubeck et al. 2020). While addressing these practices, teachers in schools are faced with complex decisions and dilemmas regarding the resumption of training and competition in the current circumstances. Certain schools have proposed a framework that is a timely minimum baseline of standards for how resumption of PE education and sports activities will occur, cautiously and methodically, based on the best available evidence, to optimise teachers and community safety (Evens et al. 2020). The majority of schools in this framework include all community and individual sports participants, parents/guardians of participants, spectators, officials and volunteers, and sports organisations are expected to play their part in helping slow the spread of COVID-19. Education of PE teachers and sports lovers in the primary schools about strategies to minimise the risk of COVID-19 is crucial (Goldstein 2020). Polet et al. (2019) argue that education has the power to promote and set expectations for teachers to follow required behaviour before recommencing sports and other activities. Improved health literacy, including awareness of the need to self-monitor respiratory symptoms (even if mild), is an absolute necessity for teachers. Primary school teachers may benefit from a consultation with local government and public health authorities and international health bodies such as the World Health Organisation (WHO) on available educational materials and options. In particular, the WHO has published proposed guidelines to be followed during the planning and the resumption of any organised events. These guidelines address five fundamental questions for any primary school wanting to resume sports events and related activities. All these questions have to be incorporated into a risk assessment tool developed to guide event organisers in primary schools, in mitigating the spread of COVID-19 (WHO 2020). The questions are as follows:

1. Is there documented active local transmission of COVID-19 (community spread) in the country that will be hosting the events?
2. Are there multiple venues, cities or countries hosting the event, or is it held in a single venue?
3. Are the participants and spectators also from destinations outside the province? Do those provinces have documented local transmission of COVID-19 which is still active, i.e. documented community spread?
4. Are most of the participants or spectators expected to be high-risk for becoming infected and developing severe COVID-19 disease? This category includes people over 65 years of age, or people with underlying chronic medical conditions.
5. Does the event involve contact or non-contact sports (where contact sports are considered a higher risk for transmission of COVID-19)?

Pedagogical praxis for implementing PE curriculum

In the South African context, the Continuous Assessment Policy Statement (CAPS) is legislated with the enactment of the curriculum framework responsible for the development of both teachers' and learners' gross and fine motor skills fundamental in the FP (DBE 2011; Innerd, Azevedo & Batterham 2019). The research conducted by Nhlongo (2015) stresses the significance of physical and motor development as part of the holistic development of teachers. This is consistent with the promotion of positive attitudes and values aligned to play, movement, games and sport as part of Life Skill education. Gumbo, Magonde and Nhamo (2017) state that the main purpose of PE in the curriculum is to systematically harness perceptual and locomotor development, rhythm, balance and laterality for learners in their early years. To achieve this, CAPS (DBE 2011) stipulates a compulsory two hours for the PE curriculum across four grades to allow the FP teachers to integrate games and some activities in the teaching of PE through participation in sports promoting physical growth, development, recreation and play. The anticipated delay in the resumption of school sports and PE curriculum could take longer than anticipated because of the real possibility of flare-up during these activities in schools (van Tuyckom, Scheerder & Bracke 2020). According to the DBE (2020), the schools are hesitant to start inter-school matches because of the risk of mixing learners from different types of community, which seems to be driving the infection rate high. This study therefore seeks to shed some light on the question of what the experiences are of FP teachers who teach PE as part of Life Skills curriculum during the COVID-19 pandemic.

COVID-19 has resulted in the school sports teachers focusing on how best to solve this complex challenge facing schools concerning the resumption of sports activities and PE curriculum. Some of the pertinent questions, according to van Tuyckom et al. (2020), linger upon what happens to teachers when their participation in sport happened without testing? How likely are PE teachers to address multiple key questions, such as how to monitor athletic performance, injury and other feedback about training owing to the physical

distance between teachers and learners (Evens et al. 2020)? In sports, both technical and physical skills are an absolute priority, and the demand for these skills could limit the prospect of resuming sporting activities sooner as the majority of PE teachers are vulnerable to contracting COVID-19. This inadvertently changes teachers' programmes owing to the lack of proximity between teachers and learners leading to the scrapping of technique-based teaching during PE in favour of strength practice (Osborne et al. 2016). Professional development of togetherness and belonging within teams and squads is likely to be altered for years to come (Evens et al. 2020).

Challenges associated with the resumption of sports events and activities in the midst of the pandemic

The global shutdown of competitive school sports such as rugby, soccer, boxing, wrestling, netball, swimming and fitness classes have raised great concern in the entire sporting fraternity. Many organisations financially support schools as part of corporate social responsibility (CSR) and nation-building (Grimit 2014). The COVID-19 outbreak, according to disaster regulations, requires the DBE to suspend sports activities and events indefinitely, handing the panic button to teachers as custodians of school sport (DBE 2020). The sad reality, according to Ramagole, Janse van Rensburg and Pillay (2020), is that rural primary schools do recruit talented teachers who are good role models in sports to inspire confidence to embark on sport-based learning during PE, the use of teamwork and a collaborative approach to teaching (Chelladurai 2007). These teachers are looking to government for a solution to ease restrictions as a desperate measure considering that their jobs are threatened. However, the increase in COVID-19 new infection amongst the teachers has forced Unions (SADTU, NATU, PEU, NAPTOSA, EUSA) to contemplate closing schools (DBE 2020).

Most sports activities performed during the regular lunch breaks and PE periods are synonymous with contact sports which are extremely challenging for primary school teachers to supervise under COVID-19 health and safety requirements. The DBE has prioritised the training of all staff members, including teachers who are all key role players responsible for fighting COVID-19 in schools (DBE 2020). The study conducted by Zimu et al. (2020) shows that teachers are grappling with simple health and safety requirement such as physical distancing, hygiene, respiratory etiquette and mask-wearing. In essence, most primary school teachers have been advised to display posters around training areas reminding every participant such as sports lovers about the aforementioned issues. This is one of the significant interventions adopted by the DBE to raise awareness and minimise the risks associated with contact celebrations and how to eradicate forbidden team handshakes and other challenges faced by PE teachers before sports resume (Zimu et al. 2020). The DBE guidelines approve the appointment of a health officer to ensure compliance with all these important protocols when sports resume (DBE 2020). The other noteworthy challenge revolves around the concern raised by unions and health experts is educating teachers regarding temporary rule changes that may be adopted by PE teachers and primary school teams in order to adhere to health protocols such as spitting in the fields and not using saliva to shine a cricket ball (Ramagole et al. 2020).

In primary schools, most PE teachers spend more time playing with learners compared to teaching, making it difficult for teachers to minimise the risk of getting infected (Ramagole et al. 2020). However, Straurowsky and Sack (2005) note that the former DBE took the initiative to suspend sports activities in the past, when there was an outbreak of infection among both teachers and learners, to minimise disaster. Therefore, a balance between health and sport guarantees teachers' motivation to use sport to stimulate a positive attitude towards their academic achievement (Alahmed, Yusof & Shah 2016). Grit (2014) confirms that teachers at the primary school level still need some kind of assistance during supervision and monitoring of learners during their participation in sport. The conclusion drawn from this study is that primary school teachers in the main face a higher risk from COVID-19 than learners (DBE 2020). In essence, most PE teachers struggle to integrate sports timetables with the main academic timetable to advance education and sport with the ultimate goal of uplifting both sport competition and education (Alahmed et al. 2016). The current pandemic is a stark reminder for these PE teachers of pending disaster should they fail to comply with the health and safety requirements on the playground, and in the indoor games and play areas (DBE 2020)

Conceptual framework

The conceptual framework adopted in this study was necessitated by the desire to explore the experiences of primary school teachers who are teaching PE and sport as part of Life Skills, and their views about the threat posed by the resumption of sports activities during the COVID-19 pandemic. This conceptual framework (see Figure 2) uses the relationship between physical activity, physical fitness, health and academic performance to demonstrate how much impact sports activities and PE have on the health of teachers (Hallal et al. 2006). Evidence exists that teachers are even more susceptible to the risk of contracting the virus and dying from COVID-19-related complications than learners. The prevalence and impact on health of the evident changeability of the virus have resulted in a call for action to suspend school sports and PE curriculum across

schools. In response to the need to find alternative ways to make physical activity a health priority for teachers, the main purpose of the study is to understand the current impact of sport activity and PE on teachers before, during, and after school.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework illustrating relationships among physical activity, physical fitness, health, and academic performance.

Source: Adapted from Hallal et al. (2006)

Research problem

This study investigates the experiences of FP teachers who teach PE as part of Life Skills curriculum, and the health risk posed by the resumption of sports activities during the COVID-19 pandemic in the general educational setting in four primary schools in KwaZulu-Natal. The current outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic has imposed mandatory isolation of people and closure of schools in ways previously unimaginable in human society (Jukic et al. 2020). Isolation/quarantine does not allow teachers and learners to follow their usual training and competitive schedule. FP teachers, in particular, are the most vulnerable group affected by the new regulations guiding social distancing during the teaching of sport and games during PE. As confusion experienced by PE teacher's sets in, COVID-19 automatically imposes a forced transition period in their sports careers. According to the WHO (2020), FP teachers and learners struggle to understand the rationale behind the changes introduced during sport and games when they are forced to practise outside the schoolyard and sports fields.

While the DBE understands that teachers, especially those with comorbidities, should be treated with the utmost care by ensuring PE is implemented successfully, vulnerability remains the main health concern at both policy and implementation. Internationally, scientific measures require teachers to educate and encourage their learners to adopt appropriate preventative behaviour and hygiene measures to promote immunity and protect their health and the health of the people in their immediate environment (Evens et al. 2020). Previous studies have identified the barriers that make it necessary for PE teachers to adhere to alternative sports skills training based on the learners' deficits and needs (Jukic et al. 2020; Neubeck et al. 2020). Some of the vulnerable groups include para-athletes and others with medical conditions, who may be at increased risk. Those with medical conditions need individual management (in consultation with their regular doctor(s) before returning to teaching and training learners and athletes during their PE aligned to the sports. Policy and practice suggest that despite formalisation of social distancing protocols, sports events and games used for teaching PE create vulnerability to the spread of COVID-19. This study zooms into FP teachers' experiences of using sports events and games to explore the risk posed by the resumption of sports activities during COVID-19, while ensuring a balance between health and education.

Research purpose

This study investigated the experiences of FP teachers teaching PE as part of Life Skill in selected primary schools to understand how the resumption of sports events and activities creates learners' vulnerability to COVID-19 as the pandemic rages unabated in the deprived context of uMkhanyakude District. In order to achieve the purpose of the study, attempts are made to proffer answers to the following research questions:

- What are the experiences of FP teachers who teach PE as part of Life Skills curriculum about the challenges posed by the resumption of sports and events during the COVID-19 pandemic?

- What are the challenges faced by the primary school teachers in the resumption of sports events and activities in the midst of the COVID-19 pandemic?

Method

The desire to understand the experiences of primary school teachers in their quest to resume sporting activities after COVID-19 informed the choice of a qualitative case study design. As such, this study sits within an interpretivist paradigm, as primary school teachers and the role of sport are socially complex and constructed (Yin 2014). Participants share their experiences and perspectives; hence their voices can be heard. Employing the interpretive perspective assumes that there is change, as this perspective portrays an ever-changing world (Creswell 2014), where the main emphasis is placed on the change and development of individuals, groups and societies. It was to be expected that the study of experiences will reveal both positive and negative outcomes from teachers regarding the resumption of sports and PE implementation. The method most appropriate for the population being studied is structured interviews and observation to collect thick narrative data (Cohen, Manion & Morrison 2000). This study chose a case study design in line with Cohen et al. (2000), Creswell (2014), McMillan and Schumacher (2014), and Yin (2017), as this method of gathering data was most suitable as teachers (in this case PE teachers) can express themselves freely.

Table 1. Detailed information about the PE teachers

Pseudoname	Age	Gender	Current subject
Thembi	57	Female	PE teacher
Baniti	46	Male	PE teacher
Ayazui	50	Male	PE teacher
Tholakele	58	Female	PE teacher
Keke	39	Female	PE teacher
Zakhele	56	Female	PE teacher

The data for this study was collected from purposively selected five female and three male PE teachers from eight primary schools in the uMkhanyakude Education District, Hlabisa Circuit Management Cluster (CMC) schools. These were highly experienced PE teachers whose teaching experience ranges from fifteen to twenty-five years. Three of these participants were above 55 years of age with comorbidities and based on their experience, COVID-19 presents the biggest health risk so is the resumption of sports events and activities in the schools. This investigation took place during the level 4 lockdown restriction soon after Grade 7 returned as part of the phasing-in approach adopted by the DBE. There were no other grades allowed to return to school, and sporting activities were completely prohibited for all public schools. It was strange to learn from telephonic interviews and from shared pictures on WhatsApp by participants that the primary schools partly implemented the lockdown regulations as evident during lunch break. During this time most teachers were required to supervise learners who gathered outside from various sports fields while playing their favourite sports. It is worth noting that teachers were frustrated by those learners who removed masks during the lunch break to play freely.

During the interviews and observation, important ethical considerations were taken into account in accordance with general ethical guidelines for behavioural and social research as approved by the University of Zululand Research Ethics Committee (UZREC 171110-030 DEPT 2017/133) on 26th November 2019. Individual schools were contacted through email/WhatsApp and telephone to request their participation as travel restrictions were not permitting. The researcher first informed the Principals and participants about the purpose of the study and its voluntary nature, and their right to participate or not, and to withdraw at any time they felt uncomfortable via social media platforms. Participants were asked to sign a consent letter acknowledging their willingness to voluntarily participate in the study. They were also informed about how data would be stored and disseminated solely for this study and educational purposes. They were made to understand that interviews would be tape-recorded, the observation would be done through pictures after the interview process, and confidentiality was guaranteed. All participants were supportive of telephonic one-on-one interviews which each took about 35 minutes.

The data analysis process carefully collated the interview recordings, which were later transcribed verbatim to ease the analysis process. Each participant was assigned a pseudonym to guarantee anonymity. This study adopted an inductive content analysis to explore the experiences of primary school teachers' in pushing for the resumption of sporting activities and games during the COVID-19 pandemic. In the initial stage, the transcripts were read back and forth to create an initial understanding of the way participating schools understood how their schools were affected by the sports events and related activities that create vulnerability to COVID-19. In this

process, themes were formed that covered specific topics to answer critical research questions. In the second phase, categories were formed by grouping the topics that presented the challenges faced by primary school teachers in resuming sports and PE curriculum during the COVID-19 pandemic. Although the analysis was inductive, specific observation and in-depth interviews were used to generate themes and patterns in the data (Creswell 2013). McMillan and Schumacher (2014) believe that this exploration may later lead to general conclusions or theories. In the final step of the data analysis, a draft report of both the interviews and observation results was produced, and critically reviewed and compared with the original data.

Results and Discussion

The results and discussion that emanated from participants are presented in this section to answer the main research questions. In the main, vulnerability of teachers to COVID-19 during contact sports and other activities was frequently mentioned and related to how schools implemented health playbook examples. Their experiences and eminent danger of contracting COVID-19 were some of the most cited reasons why teachers raised concerns about the resumption of participation in sport. Yet the harmful impact of non-participation in sports events and activities that arose during interview sessions with PE teachers is also presented. For corroboration, the findings are discussed and presented for each of the four participants against the background of the literature.

Challenges faced by primary school teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic

The first theme to emerge from the data analysis relates to the challenges faced by FP teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic that has engulfed the entire world. It is part of their job to organise physical activities for the calendar year, but COVID-19 has thrown the entire curriculum into disarray. They argued that a series of major and local sports events planned for primary schools by the District for 2020 were postponed, and some have been cancelled. It was evident that school and other stakeholders are working behind the scene to come up with a Plan B to compensate for teaching time lost as a result of this pandemic. Most participants were keen to keep themselves physically active, but one conclusive damper on their aspiration was a threat posed by COVID-19 during the staging of school-wide games and activities. Some participants, because of their age, carefully flagged the risk associated with social gatherings. However, the senior member of school who also teaches PE seemed unmoved by the fear reported in the media as the DBE plans addressed most of the concerns:

Thembi: In my school, the daily assessment indicates that PE and sports cannot resume under the current climate of fear as the risk is too high to take. Although the schools have reopened, only Grade 7 was allowed to return earlier than expected but the risk is even there. We are not sure how we are going to teach PE and sport to the entire FP learners when they are back while maintaining strict health and safety protocols.

The concern from this participant was legitimate owing to the serious threat imposed by COVID-19 should sports activities and PE be allowed to restart too quickly under lockdown. What sparks the fear is that the majority of learners are asymptomatic, and could easily spread the virus to teachers, making the containment effort even more difficult (WHO, 2020). Golsteyn, Jansen, Dave, van Kann and Verhagen (2020); and Thompson and Rasmussen (2020) continue to emphasise the importance of preventing and controlling the coronavirus, and propose steps that schools and parents should take to help protect children and adolescents as they resume their regular schedules. Most participants fear for their health as the rate of infections rise. Three participants opposed resumption of sports owing to high vulnerability to contracting COVID-19 from learners and other colleagues, as Ayazui shares her experience about fear of dying from COVID-19:

Ayazui: I am afraid I might get infected by COVID-19 from learners as like to engage them during sports and games during PE. PE must be suspended until it is safe to resume. Remember learners in the FP are playful in nature, which can trigger contamination, and inadvertently transmit the virus. Worse, the majority of FP teachers like myself are diabetic, with other serious comorbidities; this virus is invisible and highly contagious and lethal.

The health scare is serious. According to Neubeck et al. (2020), schools should continue to impose restrictions on physical activity that involves contact between learners and teachers, or contact with shared equipment (e.g. balls). As part of the containment measures, innovative teaching strategies need to be implemented, including Internet-based, virtual delivery of classes to minimise direct student-to-student and student-to-teacher contact (Ramagole et al., 2020). Participants argue that online learning is necessary to give assurance to teachers that PE education and sport do not jeopardise the health of teachers and learners. It is necessary to protect everyone who might be at risk should anything happen to members of the school community. The worst-case scenario, according to Baniti, was expressed as follows:

Baniti: "Working with learners during the PE period is the most rewarding exercise no money can buy. But now this pandemic has turned my passion for sports and PE from bad to worse. I am always afraid of anything I touch or see, even my learners and colleagues.

Thembi: Teaching Grade 7 alone is a huge responsibility, as you can imagine. As you teach them, you hardly concentrate on your work because of the fear in your conscious mind. In a nutshell, these learners are not disciplined, and some don't believe the virus exists, hence too many threats are lingering over our health and safety.

Jukic et al. (2020) argue that the benefit of sport and PA cannot be overstated because of its long-term impact on improving learners' physical and mental wellbeing, and helping them to develop teamwork and leadership skills in later years. However, scholars caution that sports and physical activity expose PE teachers to COVID-19 infections, hence, for many schools, resumption of sports is a distant dream (Ramagole et al., 2020). As COVID-19 spreads faster in South Africa, teachers and learners should remain vigilant and mindful of the recommended infection prevention and control measures if sports and physical activities are to resume (Chen et al., 2020).

Sports events and activities create vulnerability to the spread of COVID-19

The COVID-19 pandemic may result in psychological distress for teachers and their families. Participants are aware that if stress and trauma are not detected and addressed, they may cause long-term harm to learning and overall wellbeing. Most participants argue that this can lead to burnout, resulting in high rates of absenteeism and even in teachers leaving their jobs. The experience of having to spend sleepless night thinking about death is traumatic on its own says Thembi, she further stated that:

Thembi: Dealing with this pandemic is a really traumatic experience, and sometimes diminishes the love for the profession.

The report by the WHO (2020) places school leaders at the centre to ensure that teachers and education support staff receive ongoing psychosocial support. This is critical for teachers who also need to provide support to learners and families. Organised sports participation in primary schools forms the fundamental basis for running successful PE, but the whole health crisis has been overshadowed by the negative experience for PE teachers and vulnerability associated with sports events and other physical activities. The sad reality is that our understanding of coronavirus as teachers needs to change as they experience negative stories every day the argument advanced by both Keke and Ayazui propound below:

Keke: Knowing what we know now, it is difficult to allow the resumption of sports and PE curriculum as we used to before lockdown. Some of us have underlying conditions which make us vulnerable to contracting COVID-19. This is heightened by stories in every news platform about people we know dying. Ayazui: Our ages and other conditions make it difficult to run PE with any degree of confidence and certainty. Remember that even parents and teacher unions have learned so much about this pandemic, and are continually putting pressure on us by reminding us of impending vulnerability from the sport for all in the school.

One of the conclusions drawn from the findings was that the resumption of PE and sports activities is a tricky challenge for schools. The most troubling challenge revolves around physical contact between teachers and learners – sharing personal protective equipment (PPE), braces and towels, drinking vessels, showers and locker rooms – which are problematic and should be avoided (WHO, 2020). Participants also noted the challenge of how to deal with athletic surfaces such as mats, artificial turf, dirt and grass; and gym or weight room equipment can all be responsible for the transmission of infection (Polet et al., 2019). Also, certain organised sports carry specific risks; for example, practising karate at close quarters makes participants especially vulnerable to skin infections and contracting COVID-19. These are some of the practical realities that fuel fear and negative perception about this virus as these participants relay their experiences in their schools

Baniti: There are many issues to address if we want to practise social distancing and hygiene successfully. Our school had to first secure the services of local community members to take care of screening and cleaning surfaces where learners have touched. but these cleaners are lazy.

Tholakele: As a school, we are committed to ensuring that everything that puts teachers and learners into danger receives the attention it deserves. Our PE class is suspended indefinitely to avoid any chance of contracting the virus.

The first two weeks were used for training teachers to take proper personal hygiene precautions such as handwashing, showering, and proper laundering of uniforms and practice clothing on a daily or regular basis. Avoiding sharing drinking vessels (water bottles, ladles, or cups), mouth guards, towels, braces, batting helmets, PPE, bars of soap, bath sponges, razors or electric shavers was emphasised (Davis, 2020). All these precautionary measures are not enough to resume sports activity and PE curriculum with any degree of certainty.

Impact of inactivity and non-participation in sports and PE

Young learners' participation in sport is one of the primary objectives of PE. The results show that sport not only ensures PA, but increases PE time as a precautionary measure to resuscitate the PE curriculum. It was

evident that not all schools have allowed FP learners to return, but the results show that even the best school PE programmes do not address PA to meet health recommendations. Nevertheless, while the pandemic has limited the extent to which people, including both athletes and the general population, can move around, exercise and socialise with one another, contradictory evidence is also emerging that many are more aware of the importance of PE activity (Evens et al., 2020; Potts & McKenna, 2020). Two participants were convinced that clear evidence about the long-term impact of the virus on sport is only momentarily showing its ugly face, and is beginning to unravel. They were convinced that PA remained a priority for learners, and they had noted serious consequences of inactivity related to child obesity and lapses in concentration.

Tholakele: Most of us have gained weight, to such an extent that it was difficult to attach one reason to their physical condition. They blamed lockdown as the main contributing factor.

Zakhele: Yoooo – most PE teachers looked terrible and lazy; it's a worrying signs of more problems to come as the suspension of sports activity and PE is indefinite. As such, teachers will be exposed to lifestyle disease for many years to come due to inactivity.

The study conducted by Foster and Roberts (2019) highlights the health benefit of PA, and cites evidence of a link between improved academic performance and physical activity and participation in sport. However, the education sector had suspended all sports and PA based on best health advice. These two teachers felt that the decision was justified despite the impact of inactivity on teachers and learners. The impact seems devastating from a health perspective; that is why urgent interventions are needed now. Currently, no one knows what sport will look like after the pandemic is over, given the early evidence to suggest that whatever caused the pandemic is likely to become a regular feature in life from this point forward (Hughes, 2020). Notwithstanding the magnitude of the challenge, participants in all four schools proposed a framework to guide the implementation of five additional extracurricular strategies to fight inactivity and promote PA, complementary to PE: (1) providing sports and PA during lunch break; (2) developing schoolyards and playgrounds; (3) promoting commuting to school; (4) developing health education policy; and (5) organising after-school sports and PA. This framework was outlined by Foster and Roberts (Foster & Roberts, 2019). It defines organisational principles that facilitate PA: promoting the role of schools by cooperation with a community partner; involving parents and pupils, and ensuring safe and recovered bike racks. The selection of some specific strategies and principles for PA promotion over others was based on the synthesis of prior evidence in research on health promotion and fighting inactivity in school.

Potential lifestyle diseases are inevitable as most public schools wait for guidance from the Department of Basic Education about when to resume PE curriculum and sport-related activities. The main conclusion drawn from inactivity is the lack of better facilities in schools and educational materials for the majority of public schools. In the researcher's observation, sports facilities are not ready for primary schools to implement social distancing and practise hygiene owing to the lack of water and other basic infrastructure. In any case, lockdown regulations make it impossible to prepare and use them, even if schools have them; but most schools do not have the infrastructure they need.

Alternative pedagogies to face-to-face teaching approaches

The findings reveal that since participants are forbidden to have contact with learners, and they have switched to fully online teaching, it will affect their teaching approach for years to come. Furthermore, the 'risk' associated with touch is now shifting to a risk associated with a different form of touch (or no touch at all) (Varea & Gonzalez-Calvo 2020). The main role of the school is to develop a collaborative approach through online platforms while making sure that it shoulders the responsibility for improving universal access to sport and activity on an individual basis with the help of online learning. Goldstein (2020) argues that schools have a responsibility to support and provide high-quality education about COVID-19 by using all available platforms. Zimu (2020) sounds the alarm that schools are grappling to enforce basic health and safety requirements that ensure physical distancing, hygiene, respiratory etiquette, and mask-wearing. According to participants, education as a sector should play a key role in reducing high risks associated with contact celebrations, and continue to forbid team handshakes to protect teachers. One of the interview responses from the participants saw online education as a panacea towards addressing the plight of teachers with comorbidities, and minimising the impact of COVID-19 during PE education and sports activities:

Thembi: Our school should begin to use online platforms to assume its role of educating learners and generally about the danger associated with COVID-19 in order to give confidence to parents and help us resume PE curriculum.

Baniti: Online education is indeed a challenge for primary schools like ours, but it is key for PE teachers as they are afraid of COVID-19, while others do not understand the implication of social distancing and their actions. Implementing social distancing remains the only viable option but a very challenging daily routine that it is difficult for teachers to get used to.

The WHO (2020) strongly advised schools to take advantage of online teaching to educate learners about the need to observe social distancing (i.e., the WHO recommends maintaining at least a one-metre distance between

learners and between school staff, and anyone who is coughing or sneezing). Most participants noted that implementing social distance and hygiene is only possible when teachers and learners work together to weather the storm while perfecting online learning pedagogy. The DBE (2020) acknowledges that indeed schools are challenged by the online teaching mode, but they cannot shy away from the legislative mandate of providing education about the COVID-19 pandemic so that PE lessons and sports can safely resume. Chen (2020) concludes that fear seems to be the last option for teachers as frontline workers and learners. Teachers have the necessary skills and knowledge needed to switch to online platforms in primary schools to completely avoid physical contact with their peers and learners during sports activities (Foster & Roberts, 2019).

Conclusion

This study concludes that FP teachers have acknowledged the threat posed by COVID-19 to curriculum implementation and learners' physical health. Extracurricular activity for most of the teachers has been disrupted, and as a result teachers have been terrified to welcome back learners who were obese and not physically fit for the school. It was clear that PE teachers were not keen on having face-to-face PE experiences such as sports events and other physical activity (such as aerobics) targeting weight loss. The COVID-19 pandemic poses a greater threat to human health than any other disease to date. On account of their years, most teachers have underlying conditions that make them more vulnerable to contracting the virus when they teach PE and engage in contact sports events (WHO, 2020). This finding suggests that physical contact among teachers and learners is a real possibility, and sharing equipment will be difficult to avoid during sporting activities.

Movement, group activities and sports attire were also identified as key considerations, as participants linked them with the scope of PE. All these components are suppressed in the current pandemic time, triggering PE teachers to question the purpose and nature of PE, and by default, their professional identity as PE teachers. Furthermore, they also demonstrated how much they miss their direct and physical contact with learners, and their concerns regarding the teaching of a “hands on” subject such as PE through digital technology. The participants' roles as future PE teachers are shifting, and this poses a number of risks and new pedagogical encounters which involve unpredictable relationships. Lupton's (2015) concept of “the digital cyborg assemblage” has already warned us about the contemporary theorising of the body assemblage, and its configuration of human flesh and technology. Similarly, Gard and Plum (2014) have also cautioned us about the impacts of a shift to digital PE, and this is undoubtedly happening now in Spain as a consequence of the COVID-19 pandemic.

It is common knowledge that teachers understand the implications of operating under the social distancing guidelines for the benefit of their peers and family members at home. It was clear to the participants in this study that the mass gathering of both teachers and learners during sports events and other physical activities introduces new risks that need to be understood and better managed. The implementation of lockdown regulations created lifestyle conditions such as obesity and hypertension in a short period. Evens et al. (2020) warn against subjecting teachers to an inhumane environment of very high activity, exercising and socialisation, as PA exposes teachers to the risk of contracting COVID-19.

On the positive side, if we consider emotions as a continuum rather than something fixed and pre-established (González-Calvo et al., 2020), there is the possibility for these PE teachers to feel happy again with their activities, and even to learn from this experience about how they can make the best use of technology, even for such a “hands on” subject as PE. Perhaps the recognition of the vulnerability of sport to COVID-19 can lead to the reallocation of both the public and private funding of advanced technologies (virtual reality and online teaching and learning), and other systems that will improve PE teaching and learning. Lastly, we cannot avoid worrying about the future of our discipline after COVID-19. As one of the participants effectively illustrated in her drawing, PE classes might now see a change in terms of the activities proposed (more individual activities instead of group ones), the personal space around each student, and more avoidance of physical contact.

Recommendations

Sequel to the finding of the study, the following recommendations are made:

- sporting activities is integral to child development, hence should not be overlooked due to Covid-19 pandemic. However, measures of precaution should be taken. This includes social distancing during sporting activities and adherence to all other Covid-19 rules.
- More PE teachers should be recruited in schools. This would help in reducing the number of learners-PE teachers' ratio. In this regard, learners would be able to observe their sporting activities under the guidance and supervision of qualified teachers.

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